

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine

VOLUME 2
ISSUE 11

JANUARY-MARCH ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume II, Issue I | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

MARICAR P. RELLON, PHD-IHTM

Assistant Professor III

J.H Cerilles State College

maricar.rellon@jhsc.edu.ph

“MANAGING A BUSINESS”

Business management involves planning, organizing, directing and controlling the resources, people and finance to achieve a business goal. The word ‘managing’ means overseeing the overall state and quality of business, ensuring that no flaws or problems within the organization will affect the whole business. So, what does it mean to manage a business? Is it simply the act of managing, assigning tasks and ordering staff? The first word that immediately comes to mind after managing is ‘leadership’. The capacity to lead and the hardships of leading are synonymous with the aspect of managing and being a manager.

Managing comes with many responsibilities, like a leader. You cannot lead or manage without a proper plan set to achieve a goal. Along with that, you need reliable members and workers to assign and create a smooth order to reach a goal. With resources and strict monitoring, a business can surely successfully accomplish its goals. The role of a manager is necessary to guide and monitor the state of a business. When you manage a business, it is important to remember that you are managing the flow and need to adapt to emergencies, changes and difficulties that may arise during the operation to achieve your goal.

Possessing skills are needed for a manager, such as decision-making. As a manager, you need to make informed choices and decisions that will be detrimental to the state of your business. Another skill you must develop is communication. Making a decision is not a one-way type of instruction that denies the opinion of others, but rather it encourages open discussion between members and being considerate of their circumstances when making decisions and instructions. Next is analytical thinking. The business profits, costs and progress should be recorded or kept as data for the manager to access and use as a reference for analysis to create plans and decisions. Lastly, a manager should have interpersonal skills and be able to delegate the right personnel for each task that are appropriate to their skills and abilities.

Business management is not a simple task of directing staff and workers. Instead, it places importance on the role of leadership and how it affects the overall performance of a business. Therefore, when you do manage a business, keep in mind the essential skills needed for that role and ensure that these skills will develop and apply accordingly.